

STRUCTURAL METHODS FOR ASSESSMENT OF INTERLAMINAR TENSILE PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITES IN THE PRESENCE OF POROSITY/VOIDS

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1 Introduction

Advanced structural analysis methods that account for the actual condition of composite parts are needed to enable accurate assessment of their durability and enhance current design and maintenance practices. Inadequate manufacturing process for carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy composite structural components could be manifested as porosity or voids. The defects may significantly impact performance and life of these components [1]. As such, they must be accurately measured and measurements must be converted into structural models to assess the effects of defects on static and fatigue behavior. Recent advances [2] in high-resolution non-destructive evaluation (NDE) methods such as 3D X-ray Computed Tomography (CT) lead to fundamental change in defect analysis methods by allowing high-fidelity detection of defects in composites and automatic transition of the defect information to structural analysis models.

The main objective of this work is to present a structural analysis methodology that accounts for porosity defects in composite parts under static and fatigue loading, and enables accurate assessment of their capability and remaining useful life. While most of the existing works estimated structural performance from the total porosity volume [1, 3], this work introduces the combination of accurate assessment of an individual part condition, structural modeling and analysis, including fatigue life prediction. The first technical challenge in this approach is the ability to accurately measure the defects in three dimensions and use the non-destructive measurements in automatically generated structural models. The second technical challenge is

the development of structural methods able to utilize the results of NDE to predict static and fatigue behavior of the structure.

This methodology is illustrated by refining the interlaminar tensile (ILT) material properties obtained in the curved-beam tests. ILT strength (ILTS) and fatigue *S-N* curve are essential material properties for the development of the analysis methods able to predict the onset of delamination [4, 5], which is one of the primary modes of failure for aerospace structures. However, the ILT properties are among the most difficult to characterize due to their extreme sensitivity to manufacturing defects such as porosity [6]. This work proposes the integration of static and fatigue tests for unidirectional curved-beam specimens with measurements by X-Ray Computed Tomography and structural modeling and analysis to determine reliable ILT strength and *S-N* curves. The porosity-free interlaminar tensile properties are generated for the Hexcel IM7/8552 composite tape system. The ILT fatigue properties complement the interlaminar shear fatigue properties of tape composites [7] to establish a more complete set of the basic material properties needed for prediction of the fatigue delamination onset.

2 CT Techniques for Porosity Detection

Micro-focus computed tomography is a proven non-destructive evaluation technology enabling three-dimensional measurement of manufacturing defects, including porosity / voids [2]. An industrial CT system with a 225 KV micro-focus X-ray tube and Varian 4030E series flat panel detector, built by North Star Imaging, Inc. was utilized in this work.

The system is able to detect porosity defects of less than 20 μm in size for coupon-sized articles.

The defects are detected by image processing techniques applied to cross-sectional CT slices of the 3D volumetric model reconstructed in the efX-CT software by North Star Imaging. Estimation of shapes and sizes of voids is performed by the Numerical Technology Company software. The software applies binary threshold transformation based on the pixel intensity found at the local minimum between air and material peaks on the pixel histogram (representing number of pixels at given intensity); and uses object labeling and elliptical fitting for void measurements and total porosity volume calculations. Figure 1 shows results of automatic void identification in a unidirectional Carbon/Epoxy composite curved-beam specimen. In this particular example, elliptical fits are performed in the cylindrical coordinate system associated to the radius area of the curved-beam specimen.

Figure 1. Detected voids (in red) in unidirectional Carbon/Epoxy curved-beam specimen.

Voids in unidirectional curved-beam specimens typically have the largest aspect ratio in the fiber direction, and void thickness is usually the smallest dimension. The detection method presented in this work uses slice images that represent virtual sections parallel to nominal fiber direction (cross-sections). In these images porosity / voids can be seen as thin curved dark areas along the composite plies that often degenerate into noodle-like shapes.

In author's experience, the scanning technique optimized for accurate porosity detection needs to minimize resolution, focus distance and beam hardening artifacts while maximizing contrast. Resolution of the scan is determined by the ratio of detector pixel pitch (0.127 mm for Varian detector used in this work) and geometric magnification factor of the scan, which is in turn determined by the size of the detector and size of the area of interest. CT scans accomplished in this work were done at 10.5x magnification resulting in 0.5×10^{-3} in (12 μm) scan resolution.

Another important consideration is maintaining minimal focus distance of the scan. Increase in X-ray tube voltage or current is limited by the de-focusing of the tube that is proportional (in millimeters) to the electron-beam generating power, a product of the tube voltage and current. By using 40 kV tube voltage and 400 μA target current at 0.5 frames per second, focus distance was kept at the order of scan resolution while maintaining high contrast.

Filtering of low energy protons by means of beam filter is typically recommended for reducing artifacts attributed to beam hardening. In this work this technique was not implemented as apparent artifacts were small and the minimal tube voltage was kept to avoid any de-focusing.

3 Effects of Porosity / Voids on the Interlaminar Tensile Performance

The ILT material properties are usually the weakest basic structural properties of a laminate composite system. Accurate measurements of the ILT properties are essential for the development of the failure criteria able to predict delamination failure [4, 5]. However, the ILT properties of composites have been among the most difficult to characterize. One of the major barriers to accurate determination is the extreme sensitivity to manufacturing defects including porosity. Porosity defects usually result in a large scatter in the material characterization test results. Therefore, test results may be coupon-independent and reflect the manufacturing quality rather than coupon-independent material properties.

The curved-beam test configuration is currently used in the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) Standard D 6415 [6] to measure the ILTS

of fiber-reinforced polymer-matrix composites. Figure 2 shows a typical four-point bending test setup for the ASTM D 6415 curved-beam test. Curved-beam specimens with uniform radius and thickness are challenging to manufacture due to the difficulty in maintaining high compaction pressure during the curing process; and manufacturing defects including porosity are usually present in the radius area. The curved-beam test was used in this work for evaluation of the effect of porosity on the interlaminar tensile strength and the interlaminar tensile fatigue properties.

Figure 2. Four-point bending test for curved-beam specimen.

Thirty 36-ply thick IM7/8552 Carbon/Epoxy unidirectional curved-beam specimens were manufactured per ASTM D 6415 specifications [6]. The specimen width was reduced from 25.4 mm (1 in) to 12.7 mm (0.5 in) to increase the number of test specimens. The reduction was based on the previous static tests by the authors that demonstrated that 1-inch and 0.5-inch wide curved-beam specimens resulted in similar ILTS values and scatter. Ten coupons were tested under quasi-static loading and twenty coupons under cyclic loading at 0.1 load ratio and 5 Hz frequency. Static and fatigue tests were conducted until failure occurred. For both static and fatigue tests, the failure mode was identified as delamination failure that initiates in the radius area and quickly propagates to the legs of the specimens.

Interlaminar tensile strength

Failure loads and ITLS values obtained for the ten specimens tested per ASTM D 6415 are listed in Table 1. An average ITLS of 72.5 MPa (10.5 ksi) was obtained with a 26.5% COV. The average ILTS

obtained is significantly lower compared to the 116.5 MPa (16.9 ksi) value generated based on recently developed short-beam tests [8]. The 26.5% COV is more than eight times higher compared to the 3% COV reported in the ILTS from the short-beam tests.

Table 1. Failure load and ASTM D 6415 ILTS for IM7/8552 Carbon/Epoxy curved-beam specimens.

Specimen	Failure Load, kN (lbs)	ILTS, MPa (ksi)
1	2.24 (503)	83.4 (12.1)
2	1.34 (302)	52.3 (7.6)
3	1.89 (425)	70.3 (10.2)
4	2.61 (586)	92.8 (13.5)
5	1.27 (286)	50.0 (7.3)
6	0.93 (210)	37.7 (5.5)
7	1.85 (416)	68.8 (10.0)
8	2.47 (555)	94.6 (13.7)
9	2.45 (550)	93.9 (13.6)
10	2.06 (463)	81.5 (11.8)
Average	1.91 (430)	72.5 (10.5)
COV	28.2%	26.5%

The ILT short-beam test is a derivative of the short-beam test methodology to measure multiple material properties [7]. To measure the ILTS, six short-beam specimens were machined in the thickness direction from a 106-ply thick IM7/8552 Carbon/Epoxy unidirectional tape panel [8]. The cured ply-thickness was approximately 0.183 mm (0.0072 in) resulting in 19.4-mm (0.76-in) panel thickness corresponding to the specimen length. The short-beam specimens were placed in an ASTM D 2344 test fixture [9]; and loaded in the 2-3 principal material plane in an electromechanical load frame at a constant 0.05 in/min crosshead displacement rate till failure. The fiber direction is denoted as 1; the in-ply transverse direction as 2; and the laminate thickness direction as 3 (interlaminar direction). The failure mode was a tensile delamination at the maximum ILT stress location which was at a surface in the center of the short-beam specimen. A 116.5 MPa (16.9 ksi) average ILTS was calculated and a low 3% COV was observed [8].

Interlaminar tensile fatigue S-N curve

Twenty curved-beam specimens tested under cyclic loading were used to generate the ILT fatigue S-N

curve corresponding to a 0.1 load ratio. The ILT peak stress was calculated from the closed-form approximation given in ASTM D 6415 [6]. The deformed shape used for the stress calculation was obtained from the static application of the peak load prior to fatigue testing. The $S-N$ curve was generated by plotting the ratio of the ILT peak stress and the ILTS against the log of the number of cycles to failure. The 72.5 MPa (10.5 ksi) ILTS value obtained from the ten ASTM D 6415 curved-beam tests was used. The ILT $S-N$ curve and the least-squares fit for the power-law are illustrated on Figure 3. A large scatter with a low R^2 value of 0.34 is reported.

Figure 3. ILT $S-N$ curve for IM7/8552 Carbon/Epoxy tape based on application of ASTM D 6415 closed-form stress approximation

Post-failure CT inspection

Post-failure CT scans of the static and fatigue curved-beam specimens showed that the delamination failure could be related to the presence of individual voids at critical location. Figure 4 shows typical cracks in the failed static and fatigue specimens.

The CT scans show that the delamination cracks typically pass through the longer voids located in the radius area of the curved-beam specimens. In particular, the presence of large individual critical voids explained that in several specimens the delamination crack was located relatively far away from the theoretical radius of maximal ILT stress (about 60% of the thickness). It is worth noting that the porosity content in the curved-beam specimens was low, e.g. the porosity content in the laminate thickness-based $0.26 \times 0.26 \times 0.26$ in³ ($6.6 \times 6.6 \times$

6.6 mm^3) cube volumes throughout the CT scans in the curved-beam radius area was less than 0.12%. Therefore, the large scatter and reduction in the failure loads are related to the presence of the individual voids at critical locations, rather than to the porosity volume.

Figure 4. Delamination crack passing through large voids in the curved-beam specimens failed under static (top) and fatigue (bottom) loading.

This analysis shows that porosity volume alone is not sufficient for describing the effects or severity of voids. Indeed, a single large void present close to the mid-plane in the curved-beam radius area is worse than a few dispersed smaller voids that add up to the same total volume. Ref. [10] also shows that the porosity volume often does not correlate well with the degradation of structural performance and documents a significant statistical relationship between fatigue life and the presence of large voids in composite specimen.

4 Structural Analysis of Porosity/Void Defects

Post-failure CT scans showed that the interlaminar delamination failure in the curved-beam specimens can be related to the presence of an individual void

at a critical location. Combined effects of the void geometry and position can be captured by the FE analysis of the stress concentration near the critical void.

Computational models are implemented in the ABAQUS finite element software [11]. CT measurements are transferred to FE models by using ABAQUS scripting capability to automatically build a structured three-dimensional local mesh of the volume around the critical void. Voids are represented by a tri-axial ellipsoid defined by the thickness and two aspect ratios in the fiber and width directions as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. 3D structured FE global model of the curved-beam coupon and local sub-model of a critical void.

Linear 8-noded hexagonal 3D elements with reduced integration scheme (C3D8R) were used in both models. Typical total number of degrees of freedom (DOF) in the local model was in the 500K-800K range. Mesh refinements were defined around the void and convergence of local stresses was verified. Displacements from the global model of the curved-beam specimen at failure load were applied as boundary conditions for the six faces of the local model volume. FE mesh for the global model is illustrated in Figure 5 and includes a total of 560K DOF using the C3D8R hexagonal elements. Frictionless contact was defined between the specimen and the support rollers modeled as analytical rigid surfaces; and the non-linearity due to large displacements was included.

Interlaminar stress concentration develops at the edge of the critical void and initiates delamination

failure. Stress-based failure prediction in the presence of large stress gradients require inspection of stresses (or spatially averaged stresses) at a characteristic distance that could represent some gage length related to failure. The concept of using characteristic distance to determine failure of composites in the presence of stress concentrations has been proposed in Ref. [12]. The same work introduced the point-stress and average-stress failure criteria, where failure is determined by stresses at a finite characteristic distance or stresses averaged over a characteristic distance in the stress concentration region.

These methods can be applied to the analysis of the ILT stress concentrations that develop at the critical voids under the application of a failure load found in tests of curved-beam specimens. Once the defect information has been transferred into FE models and their effects captured through FE analysis, the defect-free material allowables can be obtained from the curved-beam tests.

5 Refinement of Interlaminar Tensile Properties

The point-stress and average-stress methods were applied to the stress concentration analysis of the curved-beam specimens tested. For all specimens, critical voids were identified in the CT scans before specimen failure and confirmed as the origin of the delamination crack in the corresponding post-failure CT scans. The CT data was transferred into local FE models.

Interlaminar tensile strength

For the ten specimens tested under static loading, the failure load found in tests was applied to the global FE model to determine the displacement boundary conditions for the local FEM model. In the point-stress method, the ILT stresses obtained from the local FE analysis of the critical void model are plotted for each specimen as a function of the distance from the location of maximum stress concentration at the void's surface. In the average-stress method, the spatial average of the ILT stresses was considered. At each distance value, the COV of the point-stress and the average-stress data were also plotted. By examination of the COV dependence on the distance from the void, a unique and distinctive minimum point was identified as illustrated in

Figure 6. The distance corresponding to the minimum COV can be considered as the optimal characteristic distance; and that distance has been used to determine the refined the ILTS value. The characteristic distance of $19\ \mu\text{m}$ (7.3×10^{-4} in) was reported for the point-stress method and $89\ \mu\text{m}$ (3.5×10^{-3} in) for the average-stress method.

Figure 6. Definition of the characteristic distance and the interlaminar tensile strength using the point-stress (top) and average-stress (bottom) methods.

The average ITLS values are 124.3 MPa (18.0 ksi) for the point-stress method and 110.4 MPa (16.0 ksi) for the average-stress method. These values agree very well with the 116.5 MPa (16.9 ksi) ILTS obtained from the short-beam tests described in Section 3. The COV in ILTS calculations based on the point-stress and the average-stress methods are only 2.1% and 3.2% compared to the 26.5% COV in the ASTM D 6415 stress calculation. The low scatter and consistency found in the refined ILTS

calculations show that the methodology enables the integration of the effects of defects in the assessment of the ILT performance and suggest that the ILTS obtained is appropriate as pristine (free of defects) material property.

Interlaminar tensile fatigue properties

The defect analysis was also applied to assess the peak stresses of the curved-beam specimens failed in fatigue in order to refine the ILT $S-N$ curve previously obtained from the ASTM D 6415 stress approximation. For each of the 20 fatigue curved-beam specimen tested, critical voids were detected using the measurement techniques described in Section 2 and measurements were transferred to the local FE models of critical voids. Global displacements from the global model at peak fatigue test loads were applied as boundary conditions for the local models. For the point-stress method, the peak stress was found as the ILT stress at the $19\ \mu\text{m}$ (7.3×10^{-4} in) point-stress characteristic distance obtained from static tests. Similarly, for the average-stress method, the ILT stress was averaged over the $89\ \mu\text{m}$ (3.5×10^{-3} in) characteristic distance. The ILT stresses at the peak fatigue loads were normalized by the respective refined ITLS; and plotted against the log of the number of cycles to failure to generate the ILT $S-N$ curves.

Figure 7. ILT $S-N$ curves refined by point-stress (top) and average-stress (bottom) methods.

The $S-N$ curves obtained for both methods are presented in Figure 7. The Figure lists the power law coefficients obtained from a least-squares fit of the test data. Both $S-N$ curves are similar, with less than 2% relative error in the power law exponent. The refined exponent more than doubles the exponent of the fatigue curve based on the ASTM D 6415 ILT stress approximation shown in Figure 3. An R^2 value of 0.92 is reported for the results obtained by the point-stress method, and $R^2=0.94$ for the average-stress method. These values should be compared to the $R^2=0.34$ obtained in Figure 3, where the effects of defects have not been integrated. The improved correlation coefficients and consistency of the refined $S-N$ curves shows the method's potential to capture the effect of porosity on the ILT fatigue performance.

6 Conclusions

Manufacturing defects can severely deteriorate matrix-dominated properties of composites, resulting in degraded strength and fatigue structural performance. Although it might not be practical to eliminate all the defects in a composite part, it is possible to avoid assumptions of the worst-case scenario and address improved part durability and damage tolerance once the defects and their effects are captured. Advanced technology to measure the defects and understand their effects on structural performance could potentially enable a fundamental shift to accurate assessment of condition for composite parts. Our goal is to develop such technology and make it the industry standard

practice for structural diagnostics in the existing and emerging composite aircraft platforms.

In this work we demonstrated that (1) accurate three-dimensional non-destructive measurement of porosity/voids defect location and size can be achieved using X-ray CT-based technologies; and (2) structural analysis models built by the automatic transition of the defect information into a finite element mesh lead to accurate characterization of the effects of defects. The methodology and models demonstrated on relatively simple material scale composite test articles show that current accept/reject criteria based on the defect volume percentage approximations in the part volume are not adequate. That is a single defect present at the critical location could be more harmful than multiple defects present throughout the part. In particular, it was demonstrated that specimens with low porosity content (less than 0.2% volume) were susceptible to large strength degradation (more than 50%) due to a single void located in the critical area.

The methodology based on integration of non-destructive measurements of porosity in the failure-critical areas and three-dimensional FE stress analysis was applied to assessment of the interlaminar tensile properties of IM7/8552 Carbon/Epoxy composite. Static and fatigue tests of unidirectional composite curved-beam specimens typically show large scatter in strength and cycles to failure. Analysis of stress concentrations at the specimen critical voids has shown that a unique characteristic distance could be extracted and used to define a gage length related to failure. This characteristic distance, combined with the detection and measurement of critical voids was used to obtain the accurate interlaminar stress at failure initiation and refine the closed-form approximation provided by ASTM D 6415 Standard. Significant reduction of the scatter was demonstrated for the assessment of the interlaminar tensile strength and the interlaminar tensile fatigue $S-N$ curve, proving the capability of the method to capture interlaminar properties of a pristine material.

The potential benefits of the ability to accurately measure the material structure and transfer such non-destructive measurement into structural failure models go well beyond the curved-beam problem. This work shows that fidelity of the non-destructive

inspection needed to quantify the smallest voids that would impact structural performance becomes extremely important. Once the engineers know the part condition, *i.e.* critical defect location and size, as well as the implications of such defect on the residual capability and useful life of the composite structure, the long-desired fundamental shift from the statistics-based to condition-based structural substantiation and disposition decisions will become a true reality.

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